

ROLE OF NPEGEL PROGRAMME IN IMPROVING GIRLS EDUCATION IN DEHRADUN DISTRICT

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Abstract

The value of girls' education has been internationally acknowledged for many years but serious obstacles to girls' education still exist. Discrimination against girls that begins at birth by families, communities and broader society continues to impede a greater demand for girls' education. Keeping this in mind the govt. of India also very specially focuses on gender equality in terms of education at every level, by setting closer deadlines to meet the objectives at primary and secondary levels. Two new programs, one targeting formal schools (NPEGEL) and the other targeting girls in remote habitations (KGBVs) have been launched under serva shiksha abhiyan(SSA) to include girls in elementary education. IN this paper authors try to examine the role of NPEGEL programme in improving girls enrollment in schools- caste wise and year wise, especially in educationally backward blocks where the female literacy rate is lower than national average (46.13%) and higher gender gap than that of the national level (21.59%).

Introduction

Over the past few decades, a positive change in perception of girl's rightful place in society has taken place, Recent development in education have been accompanied by many initiatives at the government level to introduce gender natural components in curricula transaction of instructional materials and other aspects of education (K. Venugopal 2004) Emphasis in education has moved from equality of educational opportunities (national Education policy 1968), to education for women's equality and empowerment (National education policy 1986). As a result, the N.C.E.R.T. in its latest National curriculum frame work for school Education (N.C.F.S.E.) has reiterated the need to pay more attention to the curriculum and training strategies for the education of girls. Making education accessible to more and more

girls, especially rural girls. Attempts are being made to remove all gender bias and gender discrimination in school curriculum, Textbooks, the process of transaction and education as a whole. Attempts are also being made to provide scope for deliberate action on the part of teachers and school functionaries with regard to the education of girls (NCERT 1984) and all aspects of the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA), are expected to exemplify flexibility of approach and accommodation of local needs .. In rural areas, especially among the disadvantaged group and among SC/ST, some girls are deprived of education. Hence state education department give due stress for the education of the girl.

Government of India launched a scheme, known as Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) in the year 2001 -2002 in partnership with the State Governments and local self Governments.. The SSA covers the entire country with a special focus on educational needs of girls, scheduled castes, Scheduled tribes and other children in difficult circumstances. Its target is 192 million children, in 1.1 million habitations and nearly 0.85 million existing primary and upper primary schools and 3.3 million existing teachers covered under the scheme (S. B. Mohanty 2005). The following are the main objectives of the S.S.A. scheme.

- Enrollment of all children in school, Education Guarantee Centre, Alternate schools, back to School camp by 2003.
- All children complete five years of primary schooling by 2007.
- All children complete eight years of elementary schooling by 2010.
- Focus on elementary education of satisfactory quality with emphasis on education for life.
- Bridge all gender and social category gaps at primary stage by 2007 and at elementary education level by 2010.
- Universal retention by 2010.
- Focus on girls under SSA free text books for all girls, toilets, especially for girls, setting up of VECS (village education committees) & MTAS (Mother Teacher Associations)

Besides this the education of girls is a problem as in many areas girl child is neglected. The education of girls gets affected by social, religious and other family causes etc. Since the attainments of independence, many of the impediments, if not all, to the education of women have been removed. A series of committees have been set up to suggest measures for improving the educational status of girls. As early as in 1958, The Government appointed a committee under the Chairmanship of Durgabai Deshmukh to suggest 'inter alia' the measures necessary to equal access to education for girls. In 1965, the Baktvatsalam Committee report on girl's education recommended for central assistance for grant of free books, writing materials and clothing for girls etc. The hallmark of the 1980s and 1990s is the growth of more and better information on women coming in through research-cum-activist efforts and the rise of the women's studies to analyze, generate and support action (Usha Nayar, 2002).

It may be admitted that the National Policy on Education (NPE), 1986 and its revised Program of Action (POA) released in 1992 constitute major landmarks in the evolution of status of women in India. It envisioned education to become an instrument of women's equality and empowerment. It gave an over-riding priority to removal of gender disparities. The total approach centered on linking education of girls and women to broader purposes of national development and to promote in them a culture of self-reliance, a positive self-image and the capacity to participate in decision making at all levels. Further, there is an effort manifest now not only to provide equality of educational opportunity but also to transform the entire content and process of education for achieving gender equality and a realignment of gender roles to render them more equitable and harmonious. As per MHRD annual report (2004-05) of education departments, the enrollment position at Junior Basic stage (class I -V) as on 30 September 2002, in case of boys was 6,50,84,379 and in case of girls was 5,73,13,336. In case of dalit girls, experts feel education for dalit girls is saddled with multiple handicaps facing not just caste barrier but also wide spread gender bias. Literacy figure for dalit girls are a matter of concern. It stands at 41.9% as against 58.2%, for non-Sc/St girls. It is much lower compared to that for SC males, which stands at 66.6% (S. Ghildiyal 2007)

In early decades of independence there was huge disparity between boys and girls at primary level even worse was the situation at upper primary level (Mohd. Sanjeev Alarn 2007).

But almost all policy documents pertaining to education stressed on to take steps to reduce gender disparities in the available educational opportunities although girls lagged behind boys throughout the colonial period. But since Independence India seems to have made great strides in getting larger member of girls to School but still the country has lower participation of girls than boys in the system of education.

Girls continue to lag behind boys in utilizing educational opportunities in the present day India. In general, poverty, lack of educational facilities for girls and gender division of labour are described as major reasons for educational deprivation for girls (Dreze and Gazadar 1996) (Bhatty 1998, Sengupta and Guha 2002) However, the social attitudes, particularly in rural areas are still against the schooling of girls. But several efforts have made in newly born Uttarakhand state to improve elementary education in terms of quality, quantity, education for girls and other weaker sections with the help of SarvaShikshaAbhiyan (SSA). programme . In this reference the investigator feels a need to explore the role of SarvaShikshaAbhiyan (SSA) and NPEGEL program, targeting formal schools which have been launched to include girls in elementary education. with reference to Uttarakhand in general and Dehradun district in particular.

National Programme for Education of Girls at the Elementary Level (NPEGEL) :-

NPEGEL launched by Government of India in 2003. NPEGEL is an amendment to the scheme of SarvaShikshaAbhiyan for providing additional components for education of girls at elementary level. The NPEGEL has been envisaged to be implemented under the umbrella of SSA but with an independent identity. NPEGEL was introduced in Educationally Backward Blocks (EBBs). Besides Urban Slums, it is being implemented in blocks of districts, which though not covered under Educationally Backward Blocks have at least 5% scheduled cast/tribe population and where schedule cast and tribe female literacy rate is below 10% as per 1991 census. The Programme is also providing same additional components, slums development model cluster schools in the cluster, providing material incentives such stationary, introducing additional initiatives like awards, remedial teaching and bridge courses, encouraging community mobilization and monitoring, developing, strengthening planning, training and management support. Thus, special attention is also paid to adolescent girls through development of

supplementary teaching material that includes the material on women achievers, nutrition, sanitation, environment, gender and legal issues.

Main objectives of NPEGEL are following:-

1. To develop and promote facilities to provide access and to facilitate retention of girls and to ensure greater participation of women and girls in the field of education.
2. To improve the quality of education through various intervention and to stress upon the relevance and quality of girls education for their empowerment.

Components Of The National Programme For Education Of Girls At The Elementary Level (NPEGEL):-

➤ **Model Cluster School (MCS)-**

A model cluster school for girl's is a girl-child friendly school operational at cluster level. The MCSs have facilities in terms of teaching learning equipment, books, games, etc. The facilities available in MCSs are to be used for learning through computers, film shows, reading material, self defiance, life skills, riding bicycles, reading, games, etc. The scheme also provide for hiring of instructors on contract for imparting vocational and other training. These aim at improving the achievement of girls, fostering an interest in education among them, and enhancing the level of awareness about the importance of girl's education in the community. For implementation of NPEGEL, the clusters are taken up in a phased manner and those schools are selected which have shown the best performance for enrolment of girls; are easily accessible to around 10 villages/schools and have adequate land for additional civil works for providing additional classroom and toilets and playground. While selecting the location of the model cluster schools, the density of SC/ST population is also taken into consideration. The MCSs for girls are required to have provision of an additional classroom, supply of drinking water, electrification and toilet for which on time grant upto a maximum of Rs. 2.00 lakhs is provided. For each cluster, one or more of the following interventions may be undertaken within in overall annual ceiling of Rs. 60,000.00 per cluster.

Other main component of NPEGEL is:-

1. Recurring grant, which is provided to each cluster to meet the requirement of expenditure on various activities for promotion of girl's education.
2. Awards to school teachers for excellent achievement in enrolment, retention and leaving out causes of girls students.
3. Student's evaluation, remedial teaching bridge course and alternative schooling.
4. Under this scheme teacher educators are trained for gender sensitization.
5. The Scheme provides opening of additional childcare centers to meet the gap in the Integrated Child Development Schemes (ICDS) and relieves girls from the burden of sibling care.
6. Community mobilization activities and carried out for enrolment retention and learning.

In Uttarakhand the National Programme for Education of Girls at Elementary Level provides additional support for enhancing girl's education in Educationally Backward Blocks identified in 13 Districts of the state. The EBBs have been selected based on lower rural female literacy rate than national average including 4 forest villages. Girls studying in I – VIII Standards in Government/Local body and Aided schools are covered under this programme. EBBs have been selected for implementing NPEGEL are, where the female literacy rate is lower than national average (46.13%) and higher gender gap than that of the national level (21.59%). It was launched in Uttarakhand in the year 2003-04 in 36 blocks in 13 districts based on 1991 census data.

Objective

To analyze the role of NPEGEL programming improving girl's enrollment

Rate in the age group of 6-14 years.

Delimitation Of Study:

The proposed research study is delimited to district Dehradun only.

Methodology

The descriptive survey method was employed to collect the data and information about NPEGEL.

Population Of The Study:

The population for the present study is school going girls in the age group of 06 to 14 years studying in Government aided/unaided Schools (Covered under S.S.A.programme).

SAMPLING PROCEDURE:

The sample of the present study is the schools, providing the education to girls in the age group of 06 to 14 years which have been selected from two blocks kalsi & chakrota which are educationally backward in Dehradun district. The Investigator selected 100 Schools from these blocks through random technique of sampling.

Tool

For this study secondary data were used by the researcher, collected from the records of education department of Dehradun district.

Data Analysis

TABLE – 1

Enrollment of Girls in Chakrota Block under NPEGEL Programme

Year	2006-07			2007-08			2008-09			2009-10			2010-11		
Girls	T.P.	T.E.	E.R.	T.P.	T.E.	E.R.	T.P.	T.E.	E.R.	T.P.	T.E.	E.R.	T.P.	T.E.	E.R.
Gen	102	102	100	145	144	99.3	175	175	100	163	163	100	181	181	100
SC	2128	2070	97.3	2932	2869	97.8	3204	3164	98.75	3178	3150	99.1	3370	3339	99
ST	3552	3492	98.3	4571	4534	99.8	4638	4624	99.7	4671	4665	99.87	4656	4644	99.74
Others	307	283	92.2	559	540	96.6	433	404	93.30	440	439	99.77	476	462	97
Total	6089	5947	97.7	8207	8087	98.5	8450	8367	99	8452	8417	99.59	8683	8626	99.34

(T.P-Total Population , T.E.- Total Enrollment, E.R.-Enrollment Ratio)

The table depicts that there is remarkable role of NPEGEL programme, being run under SSA in encouraging the girls enrolment in schools.

The table shows cast wise enrolment of girls under NPEGEL blocks of Dehradun from 2006-07 to 2010-11. NPEGEL schemes are running under the intervention programmes of SSA in Educationally Backward Blocks, Chakrota and Kalsi of DehraDun district.

Table shows that in Chakrota block, total of 5947 (97.7%) girls were enrolled in the year 2006-07 and it is overwhelming to see that figures have raised up to 8626 (99.34%) in the year 2010-11. Enrolment of general caste girls is missed by 0.66% almost the 100%, throughout the study years. Enrolment of SC girls has increased from 97.3% in 2006-2007 and to 99% in the year 2010-11, while the enrollment of ST girls was 98.3% in 2006-07, and rose to 99.74% in the year 2010-11. In other words, a gradual increase can be seen in the enrollment of girls in Chakrota block of Dehra Dun.

Graph 1

TABLE 2

Enrollment of Girls in Kalsi Block under NPEGEL Programme

year	2006-07			2007-08			2008-09			2009-10			2010-11		
Girls	T.P	T.E	E. R.	T.P	T.E	E.R	T.P	T.E	E. R.	T.P	T.E	E. R.	T.P	T.E	E.R
Gen	116	116	100	122	121	99	136	136	100	166	166	100	173	173	100
SC	221 4	214 6	96. 9	234 8	230 4	98.1 2	234 5	229 7	97. 9	237 6	235 1	98. 9	236 4	235 4	99.5 7
ST	379 1	375 6	99 6	376 6	376 3	99.9	379 7	378 9	99. 8	354 2	353 1	99. 7	334 8	334 3	99.8 5
Othe rs	161	160	99. 4	103	103	100	102	102	100	118	118	100	124	123	99.1 9
Tota l	628 2	617 8	98. 3	633 9	629 1	99.2 4	638 0	632 4	99. 1	620 2	616 6	99. 4	600 9	599 3	99.7 3

(T.P-Total Population , T.E.- Total Enrollment, E.R.-Enrollment Ratio)

The table exhibits that another NPEGEL block Kalsi also shows the same trend of increasing enrollment. In the year 2006-07, total 6178 (98.3%) girls were enrolled in the block and at the end of the year 2010-11 figure rose up to 99.73%. This shows the impact of SSA programme. Total enrolled SC girls in the block were 96.9% in the year 2006-07 and 99.57% in the year 2010-11. In the similar manner in case of ST and Other Caste girls the data shows a remarkable improvement in the enrollment, 99% for the year 2010-11.

Graph 2

Discussion

Data reveals that girls from disadvantaged groups in rural areas have got opportunity to continue their education. It has given them exposure, which has opened the window of the world for them ultimately contributing to the goal of Universalization of elementary education.

- It is revealed that the NPEGEL programme which is being run especially for girls, has remarkable role in encouraging girls' enrolment in schools. This scheme has been operationalized in the year in 2003-2004 in educationally backward blocks in the district, where female literacy rate is below the national average and gender gap in literacy is higher than the national average.
- Data reveals that class and category wise enrolment through the different interventions under NPEGEL program exhibit increasing trend.
- Data also revealed that as much as 90% parents are now expecting that their dream of their daughters' education could come true. They were found to be satisfied with their daughters overall progress in school.

- Enrolment of girls in NPEGEL blocks (Chakrota and Kalsi) shows increasing trend. The provision of life skill programmes and income generating activities under NPEGEL has facilitated them to establish themselves in their life and contribute to their society. It has generated hope and aspirations among SC, ST parents to visualize a better life and living in future for their daughters.
- This study is in tune with the study of MandalPushpa (2009) NCERT, Shah Payal(2011),Shah Manjiri (2010),Saxena R. R.(2000).Sharma A.k.(2007).

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